

Emerging Issues and Challenges in Higher Education System in India

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Abstract

Education is considered to be the highest significant factor and is a basic instrument for the development of the country. India is a developing country and the best method to achieve its goals is by strengthening its education system. It should be changed from time to time based on the changing scenario of the society. Education basically provides an opportunity which has a reflection upon the social, economic, cultural and spiritual issues which are faced by all human beings in the society. In order to drive the economy forward, India needs more efficient and educated people. There are many people in India with different skills and capabilities and to make India prosperous in the global economy, strengthening the general and higher education system is a must and this can be done only by the process of research and development. The main source of creation of human capital is only through education. This is a must for economic growth of the country as well. The externalities which are generated by human capital are the main source of self-sustaining economic process in the country. This paper mainly highlights the overall performance of higher education system in the Indian economy. There are various initiatives which are taken by the government mainly to raise level of education system. The emerging issues and challenges in the field of Higher Education in India are highlighted in this paper. It is a must that a combination of various stakeholders, students, industry, educational institutions, parents and government work together for the upliftment growth of the country. This paper mainly focuses on the most desirable opportunities and obstacles that will arise in education filed in the long run.

Keywords: higher education, financing, issues, challenge, economic growth.

Introduction

“Just as plants are shaped by cultivation and humans are shaped by education”

Higher education plays a very significant role in a developing country like India as it motivates and encourages increasing human development in the country. There has been a phenomenal and rapid expansion in the field of higher education in India since independence. India has produced many scientists, engineers, technologists, doctors, and teachers etc. who are in great need and demand all over the world. India is considered to be in the top ten countries of

the world mainly because of its industrial and technological capacity. India has also made huge contribution of manpower at the same time provides in the field of technical education. India has even left its footsteps in the era of knowledge explosion. It has showed its best performance in nuclear and space domains. In the coming few decades will be heralded by space craft, satellites and others offshoots related to scientific enquires. Higher Education provides huge opportunities to the people in the society in fields related to social, cultural, moral, economic and spiritual problems facing humanity. Through higher education we can get specialized knowledge along with skilled personnel for national development of the country. The increasing youth population can be a great asset to the country if potential employability is brought to execution. Education is the key to achieve sustainability. It is often stated that the density of a nation is shaped in classrooms. Human capital can be increased only through education and this human capital is a core of economic progress in the country.

The Current education system in India has changed too much compared to what was followed in the traditional times. In India, the government has put in too many efforts to mainly achieve the objective of inclusive growth in the country. The main change in the percentage of literacy rate in India which can be seen over the years is because of the education sector. By improving the country’s education status the government not only enhances the standard of living of the people but also achieves other objectives like, the problem of overcoming poverty and unemployment, issues related to social equality, equivalent income distribution, etc. Education not only helps in contributing to the individual’s well being but also helps in the overall development of the country. These days, education is not only the means of enhancing efficiency but is also an effective instrument for the purpose of widening and augmenting participation along with upgrading the overall quality related to personnel and social life. Thus, the significance of education can’t be ignored. The period of early nineties has witnessed immense growth and development and there has been a higher degree of demand by the expansion of elementary education. The government has looked into the issues of both primary as well as secondary education and has tried resolving the issues to a great extent.

Even after so many changes having been made in the society with regard to change in the socio-economic development education pattern, our education system still lags behind when we compare it with the present competitive scenario. The major issues which our country faces with regard to education are the lack of quality education along with the slow motion in growth and expansion in the education sector. There are two kinds of people which we see these days in our society one are those who are equipped with high quality education and the others who are deprived people who fight continuously with poverty and issues related to unemployment. The people who have quality education always get opportunities in better positions. Education and economic growth of the country both are related to each other. Through the application of knowledge a person can not only improve his quality in labour but also the quality of physical capital.

Objectives of the Study

1. To examine the current scenario of higher education system in India.
2. To study the Emerging issues related to higher education in India.
3. To study the Emerging Challenges of higher education in India.
4. Suggestions and Recommendations for improving quality of higher education.

Review of Literature

The first education commission (1948) which was formed under the chairmanship of Dr. Radhakrishnan was appointed mainly to inspect the state of education in India along with

making necessary recommendations for the purpose of improvement. In order to finance education in the right way the commission suggested that education should be placed in the Concurrent list.

Pillai (1962) studied the history and the issues related to educational finance in both primary as well as secondary education sectors in various sectors. The study found out that the cost of education in relation to the total revenue of the state was too expensive. Positive suggestions were made for reducing the expenditure on education.

Datt (1969) examined the cost of education in various colleges. Raw data was collected from 30 colleges and the expenditure was specified into salary, equipment and co-curricular activity etc. He studied this using the technique of correlation and regression.

Raj (1971) made a note on the ever growing growth in the number of students who are going for higher education.

Coombs (1972) have given detailed explanation stating the reason as to why the cost analysis has become imperative in the current scenario. Recommendations were further given that cost analysis is a powerful and necessary tool for effective educational organization growth and planning.

The Commission on Higher Education (1973) examined that the financial issues being faced by higher educator in different states. The Commission amended that “in the present century, the public share of college costs has been rising and this increase is largely due the growing proportion of students”. The Commission called for a reappraisal of traditional views of higher education. Recommendations were made for careful study of this issue.

According to Altbach (2004), “India has different significant advantages in the twenty-first-century knowledge race. India has the largest education sector which is the third largest in the world after China. English is used as a primary language of higher education and research.

Panagariya (2010) studied that although the ailments of Indian Higher Education System are wider than those of the British system, there are useful lessons for us to learn from. This is done basically to increase investment in education and ensure that the quality of teaching.

Walia (2011) examined that higher education has made a significant contribution to economic growth and development along with social progress in the economy.

University Grants Commission (UGC) (2011) in the examined, “Need to Improve Quality of Higher Education”, which states that as per the report of the University Grants Commission, the number of students opting for higher education is increasing day by day.

Research Methodology

The present study is descriptive cum exploratory. It is based on both primary and secondary data which is collected from various sources. These sources include national reports, economic surveys, websites etc. of state and national level departments of the education sector. The analysis has been done on different indicators, like Gross Enrolment Ratio, Drop-out rate etc.

Major Objectives of Higher Education in India

1. **Wisdom and knowledge-** Education involves both training of minds as well as souls. The training provided should give knowledge and wisdom. Factual information would help an ordinary man to be educated unless something is awakened in him. Therefore, there should be inculcation of both wisdom and knowledge together.
2. **Aims of the social order-** Our education system must necessarily help in finding its guiding principle in the aims of social order. The country cannot Preserve its freedom unless and until it preserves the value of democracy, justice, liberty, equality etc.
3. **Love for higher values of life-** The greatness of a country does not depend on its territory alone or on the length of its communicationbut it mainly depends on the love for higher values of life. It is necessary to develop a thought for the poor and sufferings, respect for women, faith in brotherhood regardless of race, religion etc.
4. **Training for leadership-** One of the significantobjectives of higher education is the training for leadership in both personal and professional life. It is the main duty of all the universities to train men and women for the purpose of wise leadership.

Issues in Higher Education System in India

There are a number of issues which India faces in relation to illiteracy, poverty, lack of employment, problems related to moral and spiritual values etc. But in the recent years every individual of a nation is concerned with the issue related to education. Some of the common issues are mentioned as under-

1. **Teaching quality-** The first issue that higher education in India is facing mainly because of the decreasing teaching quality. The teachers appointed are not well trained and qualified for the job. This effects the students to a great extent. Most colleges these days recruit young graduates as professors who lack experience and knowledge which becomes a big issue.
2. **Financing-** India spends too much on education sector but does not get back the fruitful benefit in return which is again a major issue the country is currently facing. However if the quality of higher education has to be improved then more financing is required.
3. **Privatization-** This is a major issue that higher education faces. Privatization will not be helpful in solving the problem. It is necessary to foster the culture of creativity, imagination along with learning of new skills in young minds of students.
4. **Quota System-** As far as possible the quota system must be removed as it creates a bit of impartiality for the students who really deserve. Quota system is not good for the quality of higher education.
5. **Political Factor-** Political influence is considered to be a big barrier with higher education. Governing bodies usually do not prefer any kind of political influence or interference in their dealings and associations.

6. **Moral Issues-** This is considered to be a big obstacle for education as younger generation is not interested in serving their country. They are more interested in just taking up a job with a good pay.

Challenges in Higher Education System in India

Since India has got independence it has been facing various challenges in order to establish a strong education system. There were different governments which were formed over the years who framed different policies and procedures for the working of the education system in the right manner, but all lacked efficiency in working for a long time.

Currently the education sector in India is facing a lot of problems. The new global scenario poses unprecedented challenges for the Indian higher education system. The University Grants Commission has stated that a wide range of skills will be demanded from the graduates of various professional disciplines which include agriculture, law, management, medicine etc. The general mode of education which India has been imparting to its students over the years can no longer be continued. Huge amount of investment should be made to make human resource productive and to enhance knowledge with skills which will be helpful in developing appropriate attitudes.

Internationalization of Higher Education i.e. globalisation has given rise to the increased competition among various educational institutions these days. The overall scenario of global quality standards does not match the higher education in India. Focusing on the quality of education is a must in order to cope up with the current education standards. It is must to examine and understand the policies related to internationalization of higher education which will help in giving a clear idea about the mechanism working and how it will be allowed to impart education in the country. Keeping in mind the emerging needs the UGC stated that university has a very important role to play in promoting the social change in the country. It must make an impact on the community if it is to retain its legitimacy. This will be beneficial to gain public support as well. This can be done only if universities in India emphasis on community based programmes and work on the different social issues and concerns. The system should be effective as well as efficient for smooth operations. Therefore, the management of higher education has become a significant concern for effective management in the country. This shift is possible only through a systemic approach. Development of human resource and networking the system through information and communication technology is a must. India faces many challenges with respect to higher education in India. These include inadequate infrastructure and facilities, vacancies in faculty positions along with poor quality in teaching.

Apart from these the other common challenges include low student enrolment rate, outmoded teaching methods, fall in the research standards, lack of motivation amongst students, gender, ethnic imbalances etc. One of the major challenge India faces is to provide higher education for students coming from poor families. Students from poor background face too many problems as they are not academically prepared to crack highly competitive examinations. Higher education does not get any financial support from government and society which is yet another drawback. Colleges in the rural areas are non-viable and are under-enrolled. They have extremely poor infrastructure and facilities. There is an absence of a well-informed reform agenda for higher education in India.

It is a must to modernize our education system so that our country can get much more technically graduated students. This will lead our country to a developed state. It is necessary for the country to stop youth to go abroad for higher education and adopt methods and make policies so rigid students pursue their higher education within the country itself. Higher education is extremely diverse in nature and the challenges faced by higher education institutions are just as diverse. Education is not only the process of digesting books. It also involves various co-curricular and extra-curricular

activities that help students to a broader meaning to life. There is a lack of universities and institutes for education but one most significant fact is that the quality of education is absent in the field of higher education. The faculties are very less and the knowledge which they possess is insufficient. It is a must to make students understand that knowledge is just not necessary for grabbing a job. Students lack creativity in the current times. Students work hard but lack in adopting innovative methods and techniques to stand out from the rest. It is a must to bring about revolution in higher education.

Strategies Which Can Be Adopted for Improvement of Higher Education

Higher education in India can be improved if the following methods, if adopted in the right manner. They include-

1. **Towards a Learning Society-** India is moving towards a learning society and every human activity will require contributions from experts. It is necessary for the country to prepare itself to invest more on higher education. It is necessary to take measures to refine, diversify and upgrade higher education sector in the country.
2. **Innovative Practices-** The new technologies offer vast opportunities for progress. It helps in economic growth, good health, service delivery, social and cultural advances. More efforts must be put with regard to research and innovation-growth linkage.
3. **To Mobilize Resources-** There has been a decline in public funding which can be over the last two periods. Effective measures should be adopted for the purpose of mobilizing the available resources for higher education. Various schemes should be started for the purpose of funding students who come from economically low backgrounds.
4. **Student-Centered Education and Dynamic Methods-** Methods of higher education also have to be appropriate to the needs of learning. Student-centered education and dynamic methods of education will come only when the teachers are willing to develop new attitudes and skills. Traditional methods of lectures must be stopped to some extent and necessary workshops and seminars should be conducted for improvement and bringing confidence in the students.
5. **Quality Development-** Quality depends on its all functions and activities which include teaching, academic programs, research, scholarship, staffing, building, facilities, equipment's etc. Higher education should be characterized by its international dimensions which include exchange of knowledge, interactive connections, mobility of teachers and students, research projects etc.

Conclusion

After independence, there has been a huge increase in the number of institutions for higher learning in all fields. But the growth has only been quantitative and has not been able to achieve quality in the right manner. India has a growth rate of 9% and above and is considered to be one of the fastest developing countries of the world. To sustain that rate of growth, in the country it is necessary to increase the number of institutes along with the quality of higher education. To reach and achieve the future requirements of the country it is a must to rework on the Financial Resources, amount of Equity, quality Standards, relevance and responsiveness to a great extent.

The Higher Education system in India has witnessed many transformations and reforms over the years. One of the main reasons for this transformation was globalization of economic activities along with growth and development in science and technology. Various resources have been found over the years and implementation of these resources have been done in the right manner in the field of higher education. The institutes of technology so formed have proved to be of great success in terms of providing better quality education in different fields. But one major concern with regard to these institutes was the cost factor which was not possible for all students of different classes to afford. Higher education in India plays a major role in the society. It is of importance to many and reforms so formed and the policies implemented serve as a threat to specific and social arrangements that provide benefits to powerful groups. It is often seen that most of the good policies are yet not implemented in country. If it would have been done in the right manner, would have led to the development of the country way back. The main reason being politics. Language was also a major barrier in this field. To conclude, Higher education in India is very important part of the modern Indian society. It has also intertwined itself in the political and social systems of the society. This higher education system is in need of change, growth and development. In order to effectively plan and implement the same for the purpose of improvement, it is a must that realistic perceptions of what is possible and what is not should be made in a clear manner.

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